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A consistent formulation based on continuum mechanics for modelling strain softening in composite materials

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Abstract: To meet damage tolerance requirements in the aerospace industry, structural designers have increasingly adopted predictive numerical tools to model damage onset and evolution over the years. Composite material structures modelling, for example, presents a direct relation between model fidelity and computational cost, potentially leading to greater design iterations and costs. Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) benefits from the smeared cracking approach and displays the potential of high fidelity associated with efficient modelling. Conventional CDM models were initially developed under assumptions that may lead to inconsistencies at large deformation analysis. This work presents a brief review on the fundamentals of progressive damage formulations for intralaminar damage and proposes a novel consistent methodology. Analytical results were generated for an elementary level validation for both current and proposed methodologies. These models were implemented as user material models in Abaqus/Explicit and dependency on the element size discussed. A coupon level validation was conducted for each formulation, where the same dependency was noted allowing for conclusions to be drawn.

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1. Introduction

High performance structural behaviour has been the main application for composite materials since their introduction. For the aerospace industry, however, the increase in performance must be achieved without compromising safety levels. While in one hand, composites display a potential for structural design optimization, on the other, time-consuming complex modelling and tests are necessary. Predictive numerical tools for damage propagation suffer from the rapid increase in computational cost associated with result quality. A cost-effective

solution is the smeared crack approach, where damage evolution can be related to the Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM). Many progressive damage models are implemented in Finite Element (FE) codes, such as [1-4] for interlaminar damage, and [5-8] at intralaminar level. However, some hypotheses can be consistent only for geometrically linear problems and can introduce errors at large strains. This work focuses on the development of an intralaminar progressive damage material model for FE analysis, suitable for large deformations, in opening mode for regular meshes.

2. Methodology

2.1. Continuum damage mechanics for one-dimensional strain field

Composite materials failure and cracking can be modelled by the CDM, which consists in progressively reducing the stiffness of regions that satisfy a set of onset criteria. Eq. (1) displays the stress (σ) x strain (ϵ) relation for a uni-axial strain field. The stress value can also be computed from the material point opening displacement (δ), leading to a Traction Separation Law (TSL), where the area within the envelope is the critical Strain Energy Release Rate (SERR). Assuming a bi-linear TSL, stiffness damage variable (D_k) is related to separation as in Eq. (2). Constitutive stiffness damage variable (D_E) depends on the separation, strain and stiffness damage values, as in Eq. (3). For linear elastic materials under small strain conditions $K\delta = E\epsilon$ and both damage variables are equivalent.

$$\sigma = (1 - D_E)E\epsilon = (1 - D_k)K\delta \tag{1}$$

$$D_k = 1 + \frac{\delta_0 (\delta - \delta_f)}{\delta \delta_f - \delta_0} \tag{2}$$

$$D_E = 1 - (1 - D_k) \frac{K\delta}{E\epsilon} \tag{3}$$

2.2. Single element traction - separation

To explore the effects of large deformation on the TSL's, a square element with one-dimensional strain field is proposed, Fig. 1. Eq. (4) relates spatial positions x, y, z to material reference coordinates X, Y, Z .

Fig. 1. Square element subjected to uni-axial strain field.

$$x = X + \frac{\partial u}{\partial X} X \quad y = Y \quad z = Z \tag{4}$$

The product of strain value by the element size, at the desired direction, is a commonly adopted methodology for predicting opening displacements. However, as discussed in [9], care should be taken on the use of stress softening laws with different strain measures. As shown in Eq. (5), such prediction is only valid for infinitesimal displacements, where $\ln\left(1 + \frac{\delta(t)}{L_0}\right) \approx \frac{\delta(t)}{L_0}$. For large deformation analysis, the separation is underestimated by such strategy.

$$\delta_{prediction} = L_0 \epsilon_{log} = L_0 \ln \left(1 + \frac{\delta(t)}{L_0} \right) \neq \delta(t) \quad (5)$$

Material point separation prediction can be improved by updating the element size L_0 and calculating the displacement increment within the time-step:

$$\delta_{prediction}^{t+\Delta t} = L_c^{t+\Delta t} \Delta \epsilon_{log}^{t+\Delta t} + \delta_{prediction}^t \quad (6)$$

where L_c is the characteristic length associated with the element. Abaqus/Explicit FE code adopts, as default, a characteristic length of the following:

$$L_c^{t+\Delta t} = \sqrt{A_{el}^{t+\Delta t}} \quad (7)$$

where $A_{el}^{t+\Delta t}$ is the in-plane area associated with the integration point. Under the assumption of opening displacements linearly related to the element strains (small deformations), damage variable can be calculated directly from strains as:

$$D_k = D_E = 1 + \frac{\epsilon_0 (\epsilon - \epsilon_f)}{\epsilon \epsilon_f - \epsilon_0} \quad (8)$$

thus, resulting in a strain-based stiffness damage variable definition. This is the modelling strategy currently implemented in Abaqus/Explicit progressive damage material model, described [8], where characteristic length definitions derived from [7]. Separation values can be interpolated, [12], or obtained directly from the element's deformation gradient tensor, evaluated at an integration point. For a 4-noded shell element, with linear interpolation functions for in-plane displacements, the deformation gradient becomes:

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} 1 + \frac{\delta(t)}{L_0} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Regardless of the displacement magnitude, the opening displacements can be accurately predicted using the stretch ratio definition, resulting in the following proposed separation prediction:

$$\delta_{proposed} = L_0 \left(\sqrt{F_{11}^2 + F_{12}^2 + F_{13}^2} - 1 \right) = \delta(t) \quad (10)$$

By the accurate prediction of opening displacements (δ), the geometric (D_K) and constitutive (D_E) stiffness damage variables can be directly determined, thus resulting in a stretch-based damage.

2.3. Single element solutions

For the field in Eq. 4, both approaches (strain-based and stretch-based) were compared to the prescribed traction-separation envelope. Fracture energies were calculated by the integration of the traction-separation laws for each element size. Both strategies were also implemented as a user defined material model in Abaqus/Explicit (VUMAT). A single four-noded shell element with single in-plane integration point (S4R) and prescribed displacement was modelled, as depicted in Fig. 1. Both implemented user material models adopt the maximum stress damage onset criterion, which for the uni-dimensional field along direction 1 is equivalent to Abaqus's built

in Hashin progressive damage formulation. Therefore, Hashin’s and the strain-based VUMAT were compared to the predictions of the proposed methodology at three different mesh sizes, ranging from 1 to 0.05 mm.

2.4. Single mode coupon structure simulations

A coupon level model, Fig. 2, was generated to evaluate the effects of different opening predictions in a notched domain in opening mode fracture. Fig. 2.a displays the boundary conditions (BC) and mesh for a given element size. To avoid the effects of element aspect ratio, a region of square elements aligned with material directions was introduced ahead of the notch. Notch width was varied with each mesh size, to guarantee a regular mesh for crack propagation. Fig. 2.b displays a contour plot of opening mode damage. Table 1 displays the material properties for both single element and coupon analysis. Elastic material properties assumed are representative of a plain weave composite, as reported in [10]. Tensile strength and critical SERR values were chosen to introduce the large displacements non-linearity, while maintaining the order of magnitude from carbon epoxy composites properties, as in [10,11].

Fig. 2. Coupon finite element model.

Table 1. Material properties.

$E_1(MPa)$	$E_2(MPa)$	$G_{12}(MPa)$	ν_{12}	$X_t(MPa)$	$G_1^c(kJ/m^2)$
58640	58640	1400	0.04	500	200

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Single element results

Fig. 3 displays the resultant traction-separation relations for each progressive damage approach, where opening displacements were obtained from BC at the element's edge. Shaded area in the plots show the prescribed TSL envelope. A small deviation from conventional and proposed approaches is obtained for larger element sizes. However, as the element size decreases and reaches the same magnitude order of the displacement failure (δ_f), non-linear effects lead to an under estimation of separation, and therefore an underestimation of damage. On Fig. 4, the fracture energy ratio is obtained by integration of the TSL's (G_{eff}^c) and dividing by the prescribed (G_c), as a function of initial length. The proposed methodology provided a consistent formulation where fracture energy is conserved, regardless of initial element size. The element level validation provided an important insight for the use of conventional progressive damage formulations. As the element failure opening δ_f is a function of fracture energy and strength, mesh sizes with lengths $L_c < \delta_f$ should be avoided, to guarantee the prescribed critical SERR.

Fig. 3. Traction - displacement plots for different mesh sizes.

Fig. 4. Critical SERR for different separation predictions.

3.2. Coupon results

Elementary level analysis showed that as the element size decreases, an increase in the apparent fracture toughness is obtained. For the coupon-like geometry modelled, the same behaviour is observed for the small strain opening displacement VUMAT, as the softening portion of the plots in Fig. 5 are slightly delayed for smaller element sizes, as in tougher materials. Once again, the deformation gradient based VUMAT showed no dependency on the element size and maintained the same overall toughness for all three cases.

Fig. 5. Load x displacement plots for coupon geometry.

4. Conclusions

A review on the CDM behaviour of bi-linear traction separation laws under large deformations was presented and showed that the strain measure used may lead to a disagreement on energy dissipation. Analytical model for a simple domain was implemented and replicated the behaviour of Abaqus/Explicit built-in progressive damage for composite laminates. Furthermore, a user material model under small strain assumptions was implemented and showed the same relation to the element size. A correction was proposed for the separation prediction, by computing it from the deformation gradient at each step. For both elementary and coupon geometries, the proposed model showed no dependency on the element size, due to the non-linear definition of the stretch ratio. While the critical SERR and global energy dissipation errors are negligible for most practical cases, the proposed methodology leads to a consistent progressive damage formulation for large deformations. Despite the presented study focus on non-linear effects over square elements, the same energy dissipation dependency is observed for non-regular meshes and are part of the on-going research.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

CRedit author statement

Felipe Fuga: Conceptualisation; Methodology; Formal Analysis; Writing – original draft. **Maurício Donadon:** Resources; Supervision; Writing – review.

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